

Integrating library and prosopographical data in the early modern publication network of the University of Louvain (1501–1797)

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Introduction

After the Catholic University of Louvain split in the 1970s, the rare books from the Old (or premodern) University of Louvain (1425-1797) were inherited by the newly founded KU Leuven and UCLouvain. Decades later, the two sister universities share joined efforts to reunite this intellectual heritage to one and the same digital gateway. Their remarkable reassembling effort of the *Collectio Academica Antiqua* (Caa, henceforth) on the online platform *Lovaniensia* is a milestone in this renewed cooperation. As the Caa is an artificial – and not a historical collection that includes works authored primarily by members of the university, it is arguably quite representative of the intellectual community of Louvain at the time. Thus, the collection metadata potentially store enough information to draw the web of relationships of the publishing world behind the Old University of Louvain. The present paper strives to offer an interdisciplinary perspective to the study of academic communities as real-world networks, using the Old University of Louvain as case study. We apply historical social network analysis (HSNA hereafter) to the records of the Caa collection, to visualize the web of relationships of the publishing world of the Old University of Louvain, as well as to describe under a new perspective the diachronic evolution of the role of well-known, relevant figures. We use a rolling-window approach to compute time-consistent network metrics, and study the evolution of the network and the role of its components. Then, we elaborate a new interpretation of nodes' degree centrality in our scholars' network, and relate it to the social dimension of printed items. We examine the evolution of the social presence of some relevant Louvain scholars and relate it to insights on prosopographical chronicles as well as on the history of the Old University.

Historical context

The academic output during the early modern period took on various forms, such as epistolary correspondence among intellectuals, but also, crucially, as printed publications. In the wake of the revolutionary introduction of the printing press, which started in Louvain in 1473, it was customary for scholarly research to be published in printed books, pamphlets, and, much later, journals, thereby benefitting from a far larger audience. Part of this production survived the test of time – both figuratively and physically – and represents the cultural heritage of the Old University of Louvain, under the *Collectio Academica Antiqua*.

Books were never a one-person job. Not only in terms of authorship but also production, funding, and inspiration. They were the result of joint efforts. The untapped, high-quality resource of the Caa enables us to reconstruct the network of the publishing world of the Old University of Louvain. Reconstructing the identities of the Caa contributors and their acts of collaboration allow us to provide an evidence-based network of what the publishing world behind the Old University of Louvain might have looked like.

Methodology

Building upon the rich metadata of the collection, we use a data-driven perspective which substantiate in the application of HSNA, i.e., an application of graph theory to historical data. We reconstruct the Old University of Louvain as a graph, and study it using network metrics.

Our goal is twofold. On the one hand, we aim at investigating the global structure and evolution of the premodern publishing network of Louvain. On the other, we attempt to describe under a new perspective the diachronic evolution of the role of well-known, relevant figures within the academic network of the Old University of Louvain.

Representing the academic community of Louvain as a network, however, poses some challenges, the first of which is its 3-century long timeline. Taking a network's temporality into account is crucial, insofar as it could affect both topology and flow (Blonder et al., 2012). Neglecting the aspect of time may lead to erroneous interpretation of the metrics. However, Historical Network research currently lacks a standard framework to address dynamics in real-world networks.

To address the temporal dimension of our case study, we resort to a rolling-window approach. We set the rolling window to 25 years, and its increment to 1 year, and we let it slide over the network time, generating a subgraph at each passage. Each of the resulting subgraph represents the central year of the 25-year span.

Data

As described from the *Collectiewijzer Erfgoedbibliotheken*, the Caa comprises the works from and around the old University of Leuven (1425-1797). The collection is part of the rare books curated by the KU Leuven Libraries Special Collections. We received the metadata of the Caa holdings from the KU Leuven Libraries in the form of a MARC21 XLM export. We extracted the relevant records for the purposes of our analysis (i.e. contributors' biographic records, as well as books' titles and publication dates). Then, we processed the metadata using the Python library *pymarc*, and we identified the historical figures by standardizing the multiple variants of their personal names, with the help of the clustering feature of the software *OpenRefine*, coupled with a careful manual inspection and several cross-checks. From this cleaned data subset, we are able to extract the nodes and edges lists to create the network.

Results

From the Caa metadata, we derive two network: the full network and the scholars' subgraph. The former depicts the publishing world revolving around the Old University of Louvain. The nodes are the contributors to the Caa printed items (authors, printers, publishers, dedicatees, editors, booksellers, censors, and more), whereas the edges are their shared book collaborations. The latter on the other hand is essentially a subset of the main network, with an ulterior restriction, that is, the inclusion of nodes with a form of involvement in *authoring* Caa works. We consider the role of author as a proxy to spot scholars of the Old University. This allows us to zoom in on the scholars of the Old University of Louvain, thereby providing insights that are more theoretically sound when dealing with the evolution of the roles of prominent academic figures.

In terms of the node selection, we exclude whatever resembled an institution from the contributors. It is safe to say, then, that in the current visualization, nodes actually represent people.

We process the network visualizations on the software Gephi (Bastian, Heymann, and Jacomy 2009) and then upload it to the web application Retina⁷, thereby providing browsable, interactive graphs. The figure below displays a screenshot of the Retina visualization of our scholars' network.

⁷ More on the Retina web application: <https://ouestware.gitlab.io/retina/1.0.0-beta.1/>

We compute some standard global metrics (density, diameter and average path length) for each of the rolling-window subgraphs, thereby obtaining a time series of the metrics. By assessing the metrics distribution over time, we may infer that the full network experiences a tendency of expansion and loss of connection, as evidenced by the decreasing pattern of the density towards the end of the timeline, as well as by the increasing trend of the diameter and of the average path length.

Our rolling-window approach allows us to obtain a panel dataset of node-level metrics. We attempt to disentangle our results by nodes' prevalent involvement type in the Caa holdings. More in detail, we aggregate at the role level some of the main centrality metrics (degree, betweenness, closeness, and eigenvector centrality) averaged out over our timeline. We find that nodes with the role of *censors* tend to score the highest, closeness centrality, and eigenvector centrality. Taken together, these results confirm the leverage *censors* possessed in the regulation of the early modern book industry. The roles of printers and publishers, on the other hand, appear particularly prominent in terms of aggregated betweenness centrality. In a network representing the intellectual community revolving around printed publications, it is to be expected that printers and publishers would emerge as critical hubs that connect different segments of the network.

Shifting the focus to the scholars' network, we argue that the various metrics of node centrality as proxies for understanding the social presence or sociability of scholars during the era in question. These metrics potentially offer a rather historically accurate insight due to the meticulous selection criteria employed for the Caa holdings, alongside the collection's comprehensive representation of the academic *milieu* of Louvain at that time. Although these metrics do not aim to be a measure of authority, they somewhat mirror the concept of human capital, which leads us to undertake a comparison with an existing human capital index provided by Catoire et al. (2021). We find a positive monotonic rank correlation with the human capital index, stronger in the case of betweenness centrality, and weaker for the other centralities. We then investigate who are the scholars for whom these rankings go in opposite directions.

Lastly, among the various network-based measures of centrality, we propose that degree – which essentially captures how many connections a vertex has with other nodes in the network, relative to the maximum possible number of connections it could have in the graph – may be a direct indicator of the social aspect of books in an academic scope. This metric measures the intensity and the scope of collaborations associated with the Caa rare books from which we draw the network. A scholar who frequently authors numerous works with a few other scholars will have a low degree centrality. Conversely, a scholar who publishes a few books but collaborates with a large number of co-authors will score a high degree centrality. While not constituting a measure of authority, the degree centrality within the network may proxy the social presence or scholar sociability during that era.

We show a series of plots tracking the evolution of degree centrality for some scholars of influence in the history of the University of Louvain. We summarize the main results below.

- 1) Louvain scholars' *avme* generally occurs while they were alive, with their 'sociability' falling after death. Yet, we find a relatively more lasting permanence of humanists in the network beyond their lifetime.
- 2) Our analysis corroborates the demise of Scholasticism and the advent of the 'New Science', by focusing on the degree evolution of Aristotle (384-322 BC) alongside that of outstanding Louvain scholars whose area of expertise would fall in the hard sciences by modern standards.
- 3) We document a peak in popularity for Cornelius II Jansenius of Ypres around the period of the Jansenist controversy, as well as of key figures of Humanism during the 15th and 16th century.

Concluding remarks

Our data elaboration of the Caa metadata, in the fashion of Digital Humanities, and coupled with some statistical inference, culminates in the ability at one's fingertips to browse through the publication network of the Old University of Louvain. Our paper represents a pioneering attempt in integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches, within the context of Historical Social Network Analysis. While our aim is to shed light on case study of the Old University of Louvain, we believe that this approach could be generalized to the study of other academic communities. This work underlines the potential of digital humanities in grasping the complexities of historical data and revealing fresh insights into traditional narratives.

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